

‘In the Shade of Freedom’: History, Identity and Hybridity in Alka Saraogi’s Early Novels

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Alka Saraogi’s novels document the post-colonial reality of our times succinctly with a touch of humour. These are essentially narratives of our journey from colonial subjugation to freedom and finally to alienation especially from the values which informed the freedom struggle and the earliest years of nation-building in India. They point towards a possible asylum from this alienation in the humanist values of compassion and love. To begin with, her first novel, *Kalikatha: via Bypass*, published in 1998 and translated by the author in 2002, focused apparently on the transition of the protagonist Kishore Babu from a thoughtful and sensitive adolescent in the early forties to the tyrannical patriarch and social climber of early nineties. But the story is actually not of this transition but of his transformation after his bypass surgery. Through Kishore Babu’s newly discovered penchant for roaming the streets of Calcutta, Saraogi takes the readers on a guided tour of the pre and post-colonial history of the Marwaris, Calcutta, and India. Even in *Shesh Kadambari*, published in 2002 and translated in 2004, the sub-plot dealing with Devidutt Mama’s life is a post-colonial inquiry into the history of an individual, a family and a country. In *Koi Baat Nahin* (2004), the character of Jatin Da is the focal point of the history which Shashank, the protagonist of the novel, needs to confront in order to comprehend the true essence of life- that there is no limit to pain and suffering in life and that there are people in this world who suffer merely because they belong to a particular historical epoch. On closely observing these characters, who serve as the historical markers of the three earliest novels of Saraogi, one finds that they almost form a continuum- Kishore Babu’s family history covers the period from late nineteenth century to 1940’s. Then, Devidutt Mama’s history begins in the second decade of twentieth century (he was born in 1900) and winds up in 1978 with the formation of the Janata Dal Government when he finally vanished, never to come back. Jatin Da’s history begins in the 1970’s and goes up to the late 1990’s, the times of India’s initial plunge into the era of globalization. Hence on the whole, Saraogi’s oeuvre of writing covers all the important phases of modern Indian history. In the process of chiselling these characters, Saraogi discusses several other issues related to the colonizer-colonized binary, the different brands of nationalism that guided India to freedom, the complexities of Indian secularism, class consciousness, gender consciousness, etc. - loose ends that seem to tie up only in the larger debate of post-colonialism. In other words, the dovetailing of all these issues in her writings lends them easily to a post-colonial reading.

Saraogi enquires into the complexities of the native-colonizer relationship through various incidents and characters. The portrayal is not only geared to manifest the friction and conflict

between the cultures of East and West but also to project the positive interaction and intermingling between the two. Saraogi attempts to look at all possible aspects of the binary relationship and the hybrid space created by it. This paper attempts to study this hybrid space in Saraogi’s novels through an investigation of her nuanced portrayal of characters inhabiting the in-between space in terms of their origins and identities.

To begin with, there are several instances embedded in the narrative which present the native-colonizer equation stereotypically modelled around confrontation and conflict. Kishore Babu’s grandfather Kedarnath became a freedom fighter after witnessing insult and humiliation at the hands of the British at the age of fourteen while travelling from Delhi to Calcutta by train. He writes about the desperate condition of the coaches meant for the natives: “The conditions in our compartment were so bad that one can hardly express it in words. There were five compartments of First and Second class, which were not meant for the lesser mortals. There were very few Sahibs and their ladies, so they went merrily vacant.” (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 68) Suddenly, the train is stopped and all the thin and scrawny natives (most of them healthy) are forcefully segregated to be sent to the plague camp. When Ramvilas protests, he is hit hard by the policeman in the stomach with the pointed tip of his shoe. Kedar is also slapped. He writes in his diary: “The whole night, Babuji was delirious with pain and my cheek smarted. . . I shall never forget this slap in my whole life. Babuji is in great pain. His abdomen has turned blue where it was hit. Below my eyes, the skin has turned black too.” (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 69) Indeed he never forgets that insult and becomes a revolutionary freedom fighter later in life. Even Ramvilas himself, though friendly with the British, secretly nursed a hatred for the Sahibs’ exploitative outlook. During the Second World War and of course the Great Calcutta Famine of 1940, Kishore has his own moment of hatred: “A black American soldier had wanted to give Kishore a half-eaten chocolate, in front of the Firpo restaurant at Chowringhee one day. The gesture had provoked Kishore to such rage and hatred that he felt like spitting on him. Only the fear of getting thrashed had stopped him from doing so.” (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 193) To ‘fit in’ is as important to Kishore as it would be to any adolescent. Since he keeps the company of the revolutionary Shantanu and the Gandhian Amolak, he is constantly troubled by the loyalty of his ancestors towards the British. He is particularly disturbed by the fact that his great grandfather Ramvilas was friendly with Teggart, the tyrannical British officer. He can not even bear to think that he is part of the community that deceived Siraj-ud-daula in the Battle of Plassey. Quite a lot of research and an enlightening talk with the librarian of the public library where he goes to find out the truth, ensure him that the Marwaris were not directly involved in favouring the British in that battle. In these cases, the hatred for the enemy is mingled with the anxiety related to the perception of the masses about his people and therefore of his own self.

However, apart from these obvious categories of the native-coloniser relationship, there exists a third category or the Third Space in Homi Bhabha’s words that clearly states Saraogi’s position on the cultural interface between East and West in the colonial times. The Third Space is the space of meaningful cultural exchange between the two people. It is the space where the native is as actively involved in the making of meaning and cultural transactions as the colonizer. Bhabha elaborates “The productive capacities of the Third Space

have a colonial or post-colonial provenance. For a willingness to descend into that alien territory... may reveal that the theoretical recognition of the split-space of enunciation may open the way to conceptualizing an *international* culture, based not on the exoticism or multiculturalism of the *diversity* of cultures, but on the inscription and articulation of culture's *hybridity*... And by exploring this hybridity, this 'Third Space', we may elude the politics of polarity and emerge as the others of our selves." (Bhabha in Ashcroft 209)

The 'in-between' space pointed out by Bhabha is inhabited in the early novels of Saraogi by people like Mr. Hamilton, Mr. Vienna, Arthur and Jackson who are often perceived as neither here nor there but who are actually part of both the places and both the cultures- that of the colonizer and of the colonized. They are the resultants of the tradition of syncretism. Saraogi depicts these characters as humane, compassionate and often victimized as opposed to the stereotypical portrayal of the colonizers as cruel, exploitative and calculating. For instance, in *Kalikatha*, Ramvilas' father saves Hamilton Sahib's life during the Sepoy Mutiny of 1857. He does not feel the repulsion a native ought to feel in times of revolt against the repressive colonial regime. He says, "God! He too is a *meenakh*, a homo sapien. His blood is also red just like ours" (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 33) This act of compassion lays the foundations of a friendship that last over two generations. Hamilton goes out of the way to help Ramvilas' father to set up his business in Calcutta. They share a special bond of friendship which is founded on mutual co-operation and appreciation of each other's culture and value system. Four decades later, during the famine of 1899, when Ramvilas himself is compelled to come to Calcutta in search of better opportunity, Hamilton's son picks up the thread of the relationship from where his and Ramvilas' fathers had left it. Automatically both the sons step into their fathers' shoes and another long and enduring friendship begins. Later, Hamilton reveals to Ramvilas that he is actually half-Hindu. Senior Hamilton fell in love with a Hindu girl and Ramvilas' father acted as a link between the two till she breathed her last. Senior Hamilton was tortured by the thoughts of the future of his only child from this woman. "All round him he could see the plight of half-Indian and half-English children. They belonged to no one. Many names were given to them- Black Firangee, Eurasian, Chee-chee and what not. Even a bastard. No European girl would ever think of marrying a Eurasian." (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 57) When Hamilton was born, Ramvilas' father took care to keep his birth secret till Senior Hamilton's English wife agreed to adopt him as her son and to go through pretence of pregnancy to give legitimacy to the half-Hindu child. There is also a hint given of Ramvilas' father's own love for Jayanti, Hamilton's mother. Ramvilas describes that the Eurasians of Calcutta "stay between the native north or 'black' city and the Sahib's south or the 'white' city. The grey zone between them- the areas of Bahubazar and those behind Chowringhee are full of women who have property left to them by their English lovers... Most of them perhaps like to be identified with their white ancestors." (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 59) He precisely sums up Hamilton's predicament: "Everybody is your own now, be it an Indian or an Englishman." (Saraogi, *KaliKatha* 59) Hamilton indeed belongs to both the cultures. He is the ideal hybrid produced by the colonial rule- he never gets over his love for India and her people. True to this love, he never leaves India and finally dies here.

A similar character surfaces in Ruby's life in *Shesh Kadambari*: "Eleven year old Ruby had a notion that Mr. Vienna was either an authentic Sahib or an Anglo-Indian desperately trying to pass off as one. This image was based on her observation of the lifestyles of her father's British-Parsi-Muslim-Armenian-Jewish circle of friends and associates." (Saraogi, *Over to You* 43) Her pre-conceived notions about Mr. Vienna are shattered when she sees him for the first time: "From a distance, Mr. Vienna's greying beard, the chequered tweed jacket made him look like a sahib. But at close quarters, the frayed edges of his jacket over a somewhat soiled shirt and the faintly trembling hands gave him away, his carefully brushed hair and black shoes polished to perfection notwithstanding". (Saraogi, *Over to You* 44) The always hungry and constantly in need of money Mr. Vienna was a far cry from the conventional Englishman in India. To add to Ruby's disappointment, his reserved and reclusive mannerisms and his searching, timid eyes are an antithesis of the confident and aggressive body language of the average Englishman in India. Perhaps it was this difference that made Ruby feel secure in his company and in his imaginary book called *The Indian Peep Show*. The book was about the history and culture of India and Ruby felt that no one other than Mr. Vienna was qualified enough to write such a book and to teach the history of India. "He transmitted to her his encounter with the vibrancy of this vast multifaceted land. None of it seemed strange to him, the way it did to other Englishmen." (Saraogi, *Over to You* 47)

Mr. Vienna is the symbol of the syncretic tradition that thrives between any two cultures when they remain in close contact over a long period of time. He is the medium through which Ruby gets to know of the opium business of her father's family and also about his failing fortunes. Mr. Vienna had fallen in love with Ruby's Bua who had committed suicide by setting fire to herself when the family objected to her relationship with Mr. Vienna. Ruby's association with this character comes to an abrupt end when Mr. Vienna also commits suicide by drowning himself in Ganga. Ruby recalls the elaborate efforts of her father to fulfil his last wish of being buried behind the James Princep monument, close to Ganga in which the mortal remains of his lover had been immersed.

Though the relationship between Ruby's Pitaji and Mr. Vienna is not stated clearly, there are several hints which manifest that there existed a deep bond of friendship between them. This friendship is parallel to the Ramvilas-Hamilton bonding in *Kalikatha*. The only difference is that in *Kalikatha*, Ramvilas was helped by the half-white sahib while in *Shesh Kadambari*, Ruby's father helps and supports the sahib, Mr. Vienna.

In *Koi Baat Nahin*, Shashank's best friend is a poor Anglo-Indian boy called Arthur. He is the only boy in Shashank's class who behaves naturally around him and who does not perceive any difference between Shashank and himself. This novel has another Anglo-Indian character who appears only in Jatin Da's stories. He is called Jackson. Jackson exemplifies the other aspect of hybridity. Counter to all the other hybrids in Saraogi's novels, Jackson is the only one who descends into a sort of schizophrenia when he discovers by chance the history of his family. As he digs deeper into this history, he finds out that his mother belonged to a very illustrious British line of descent though she did have some mixed blood. He also learns that his

father was Richard Jackson, a poor Eurasian whom his mother married in a moment of eccentric stubbornness. Later when she realized her mistake, she abandoned Richard and her two year old son, married an Englishman and settled in England. Richard went mad after this incident and spent the rest of his life in a mental asylum while his son was brought up by his two spinster sisters. When, along with all these facts Jackson also learnt that in his father's family at least one person had gone mad in every generation, he became overtly concerned about his own sanity. "Ultimately Jackson became obsessed with his suspicions and hallucinations and gradually he lost track of the difference between reality and imagination. He started calling himself Jaikishan, believing that he was a pure Hindu and he abandoned shirts and trousers for kurta pyjama. He would write letters to himself and then tear them off. He could never recover from those eccentricities." (Saraogi, *Koi Baat* 51)¹

Unlike the other Anglo-Indians in Saraogi's novels who are more or less conformists and even victims of social codes, Jackson became an ultra-Leftist in the 1970's and according to Jatin Da, was jailed during the Emergency. Probably, Saraogi attempts to point towards the failures of hybridity through this character. The schizophrenic, divided self of the neither-here-nor-there people is another by-product of synthesis of cultures. The concepts of race, nation and patriotism become the focal points of the confusion bred by the hurried and meaningless unions as happened in the case of Jackson's parents. The occurrence of insanity as a regular, hereditary feature in a Eurasian family is used here as a ploy to root the narrative in a realistic milieu.

Kadambari is also portrayed as a child with a mixed lineage. She has a Hindi-speaking mother from Calcutta and a half-European, half-Indian father from Uganda. She looks neither Indian, nor European. Unlike most of the children in her situation who identify themselves with the Western aspect of their identities, Kadambari turns to India and insists on studying here after school instead of going to college in London. She takes a plunge into social service. She is in fact more Indian (and more aware of and concerned for the social problems of India) than most of the Indians portrayed in *Shesh Kadambari*. Like Jackson, though not with the same intensity, she affirms her Indian-ness through all that she does. Part of this Indian-ness project is her report on Devidutt Mama- the only family member who participated intensely in the history of India's struggle for 'freedom'. The need to write this report and to understand the past through a person obscured by lack of information, arises out of her need to forge a connection with that past of India in which neither her parents nor she herself participated. This urge distinguishes her pursuits from those of the youngsters of her age. Her hunt for history is thus an exploration of what she could have been. This is remarkably different from Jackson's search for his roots and the history of his family which is primarily focused at what he could not be- it is a quest that lands him in the schizophrenic world of Jaikishan which exists only in his imagination.

Another Third space is explored by Saraogi in *Shesh Kadambari* through the character of Manoranjan Vyapari, a Lal Begi. Manoranjan appears early in the novel as the saviour of Saira, the mentally challenged girl who is raped by her own brother. He keeps popping up in Rubydi's life, always in a different avatar- as the gas cylinder delivery boy, or a roadside

vendor, or her friend Aparna Banerjee’s driver- a jack of all trades. Rubydi always wonders whether Manoranjan is Hindu or Muslim. She tries to arrive at a conclusion by deducing from several facts about him. She remembers him as one of the victims of the 1992 Hindu-Muslim riots in Tengra area: “She remembered the man with blank eyes sitting under the open sky, inside a house without a roof. The year was 1992. After the demolition of the Babri Masjid. . . He sat all by himself in the middle of burning houses, braving the sun that now freely entered his roofless house. Women, children, the young and the old, all had something to say- how, along with some antisocial elements the local police officer, a Hindu, had set their homes on fire. But surrounded by rubble, that man say alone and still, filling his roofless home with his silence. Rubydi recalled making enquiries about him and being told that he was a rickshawalla.” (Saraogi, *Over to You* 75)

Later Manoranjan identifies himself as the son of Rubydi’s gardener Lali who always wore a round Namaz cap. The paradoxes of Manoranjan’s being constantly puzzle Rubydi prior to this revelation. His seemingly Hindu name and his residence in Muslim dominated areas like Tengra or Metiaburz are at odds with each other. On hearing Lali’s name, she recalls that they belong to an ambiguous sect called the Lal Begis: “Lali had at times appeared a Hindu and at others a Muslim. Perhaps he was a follower of Lal Beg, the Turkish dervish. Lalbegis were originally Hindus who practiced a curious mix of Hindu and Muslim ways.” (Saraogi, *Over to You* 126) Manoranjan as a hybrid of Hinduism and Islam is essential to the plot of the novel because the character of the central protagonist is founded on the values of secularism, altruism and social awareness. The hybrid character here is cynical of the shortcomings in both the religions. In an instance, when Rubydi is distressed by the superstitious frenzy of Hindus trying to feed idols of Ganesha with milk, Manoranjan provides her with some solace: “One night there was Manoranjan Vyapari, on TV news, sitting with his cobbler’s tools spread around him, feeding milk to his iron ahran. Rubydi felt gratified that there was at least some one in the world who had not taken complete leave of his senses.” (Saraogi, *Over to You* 210) The puzzle of Manoranjan’s religion also reinforces the fact, whether we accept it or not, that religion is an important part of a person’s identity and it acts as a point of reference in our perception of the world. Rubydi’s concern about his religion stems out of her knowledge and experience that one’s religion can make one vulnerable to violence, discrimination and even ridicule. Her sensitivity towards this issue is highlighted by the author through an almost magic realist technique. Rubydi’s normal routine is thrown into chaos every time any such situation arises when a Muslim in her close circle of friends or Muslim community in India in general becomes vulnerable to violence and bloodshed. It first happened in August 1946, when Hindu-Muslim riots began in India prior to partition. Then it happened in 1947 when Adil, her first love, “relieved himself of all spoken and unspoken commitments” and left for England. It occurred again when her cook Harihar refused to cook for Yaseen, Sudhir’s friend, because he was Muslim. The same thing happened when her tailor Usman was beaten up by Hindu rioters during the Indo-Pak war in 1965 and even during the communal riots in 1992 after the Babri Masjid incident. Rubydi was “forced to accept the fact that she had never been able to free

herself of Adil and the humiliation she had suffered at his hands. Without her knowledge it had remained alive in her blood like an incurable virus.”

In fact, nationalism emerges as an important focal point of debate and deliberation in these novels. Simon During notes that “the post-colonial desire is the desire of decolonised communities for an identity... Obviously it is closely connected to nationalism, for those communities are often ... nations.” (During in Ashcroft 125) Identity indeed seems to be at the core of all the representations in Saraogi’s novels. The characters do not accept regular definitions of their identity. They constantly question the reliability of such definitions that tend to restrict the experiences of a human being into a few descriptive words. Entire histories are woven behind the concept of identity. For instance, in *Koi Baat Nahin*, the identity of a character called William Sarkar emerges as a problematic site: “William Sarkar, who was a fair-skinned, well-built boy and an expert in everything ranging from music to sports, always used be full of anger- always ready to pick up a fight like a bull on a rampage... Last year, while teaching a chapter on nationalism, the Hindi teacher Dubeyji in his excitement called the East India Company a bastard company. William got up red-faced and fuming with rage. He threatened Dubeyji with clenched fists- “mind your language Sir.”” (Saraogi *Koi Baat* 28)¹

William is an Anglo-Indian, stuck in India, in the Bahu Bazar area of Calcutta. Identity and nationalism in his case emerge as divided categories. His loyalties are divided between the blood that runs in his veins and the country that has been his home forever. Unlike Arthur, he is unable to reconcile these two facets of his identity. Such confusion also plagues Jackson as mentioned earlier. The desire to have a wholesome, well-rounded, easily definable identity and national loyalty lands Jackson and even William into a schizophrenic rage.

To conclude, one may take into account the reader’s response to the representation of the post-colonial reality in these novels. One can not help but ponder on the myriad markers of this reality encountered frequently in Saraogi’s writings. There is a suggestion that the post-colonial consciousness can not be ignored, neither can one escape it. In our day-to-day lives we do not think of ourselves as consequences of history. But what is identity without history? In *Koi Baat Nahin*, Shashank is at times shaken out of his deep reverie to the misty dusk in the Victoria Memorial park by the shrill whistle of the guard indicating the time of closing of the park. Saraogi’s novels shake the reader out of her/his complaisant attitude towards routine realities in a similar way. One finds oneself in a misty dusk where things look unclear and yet clear.

¹ My translation.

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